

DETERMINANTS OF LEADERSHIP TRAITS EXPRESSION IN PRIVATE INSTITUTIONS OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract:

Leadership is believed to be the engine of growth for every organisation or institution, and as such the leader’s traits expression is key to the effectiveness and success of organisations. This paper evaluates the determinants of leadership traits expression within organisations and institutions. Data were analysed using STATA in a correlation framework with multiple linear regression techniques of analysis. A model equation was used to describe the relationship between the determinants of leadership traits expression and organisational effectiveness, with leadership traits expression as outcome variable and organisational effectiveness as predictor variables. The findings show that leaders personality explains 83.7% of the variations in Leadership traits expression, Organisational culture also accounted for 88.5% of the variations in organizational effectiveness, Organisational climate accounted for 99.9% variations and Decision-making characteristics accounted for 94.7% while workforce diversity accounting for 56.7% variations. Leadership traits expression has implication on organisations for decision-making and therefore must be taken in account keenly in overall strategic planning of educational institutions.

Key Words: Leadership Traits Expression, Determinants Of Leadership Traits Expressions, Organisational Effectiveness.

Introduction:

Leadership is very important in the success and growth of any organization, including private institutions of higher education. Recently, there has been a growing interest in understanding the determinants of leadership traits expression within these institutions. This research topic aims to assess the various factors that influence how leaders in private higher education institutions express their leadership traits so as to gain valuable insights into the dynamics of leadership within these institutions, to enhance leadership effectiveness and drive institutional development. This contemporary paper identifies leader’s personality, organisational culture, workforce diversity, decision-making characteristics, organisational structure as key determinants of leadership traits expression.

To thoroughly assess the determinants of leadership traits expression in private institutions of higher education, it is crucial to consider a wide range of factors that may influence leadership behaviors. One significant determinant is the institutional culture and climate. This implies that leaders in private higher education institutions are more likely to exhibit effective leadership behaviors when the organizational culture promotes collaboration, innovation, and inclusivity. Furthermore, the leadership behavior adopted by leaders is another essential determinant of leadership traits expression. Leaders who exhibit transformational leadership behaviors, such as inspiring and motivating their followers, are more likely to express their leadership traits effectively. Moreover, the personal characteristics and traits of leaders themselves also influence how they express their leadership traits. Leaders who possess these traits are more likely to express their leadership traits and exhibit effective leadership behaviors within private higher education institutions.

Review of Literature:

Leadership traits expression consists of the totality of leader’s qualities or characteristics that bring to him some sort of enablement in the leadership agenda. The traits of leaders play an important function in managing and leading organisations because it helps to maximize organisational strategy in order to achieve efficiency and effectiveness. As posited in trait theory of personality, the traits of a person focus on personal characteristics which produces certain behavioral changes which is consistent with different situations. Many factors determine the traits of leaders and may include the leader’s own personality, organisational culture, workforce diversity, decision-making characteristics and organisational climate. Leadership traits expression may lead to organisational effectiveness or disappointments in achieving the objectives of educational institutions. It is therefore important to keenly look at what determines leadership traits expression in leadership process so as to utilize its full potential to enhance the effectiveness of business operations.

Leader's personality traits are the unique or distinctive characters associated to an individual and this covers emotional and cognition patterns which are normally influenced by environmental factors. A leader's personality considers dealings with people around working environment in terms of composition and the ability to deal with different situations. The personality of leaders leads to agreeableness with people or followers and the preparedness to pay attention to situations and get organisational objectives achieved. Emotional stability which is key to leader's personality enhances the level of openness in terms of development of ideas, vivid imagination and the excellent application of those ideas in unity with followers to achieve organisational objectives. Nathanson (2021) juxtaposes that leader's personality traits is key to effective leadership. He identifies the following as the key 15 components of personality traits of effective leaders: Openness and friendliness, kindness, thoughtfulness, emotional stability, creativity, good communication, integrity, self-awareness, empathy, engagement, humorous, accountable, passionate, and respectable. These personality traits as indicated by Nathanson (2021) empower leaders for effective administration of organisational agenda.

On organisational culture can guide staff in knowing what to do and what not to do, including practices, values, and assumptions about their work in the aim to facilitate the achievement of organisational effectiveness. A strong culture is needed in an organisation if employees are to work together to achieve objectives of organisations. This culture will determine the way employees behave and the attitude they have to develop towards work and management. Since organisational culture promotes a shared belief values and assumptions it may serve as a bonding glue that brings the workforce of the organisation together to work towards the achievement of mission and vision despite obstacles. An effective organisational culture is likely to promote unity despite workforce diversity. This indeed will determine the traits of leadership in the leadership process. A strong organisational culture would enhance a positive leadership trait and a bad culture can possibly enforce traits that do not promote effective leadership. That means leaders must show employees how to embody values that contribute to organisational culture. It is the duty of leaders to communicate the company's mission, goals and core values. Organisational culture must define behaviour and actions employees take to create a positive environment in an attempt to make business succeed. Wong (2020) proposes that a great culture exemplifies positive traits that lead to improved performance, while a dysfunctional company culture brings out qualities that can hinder even the most successful organisations.

Workforce diversity means similarities and differences among employees in terms of age, cultural background, physical abilities and disabilities, race, religion, gender, and sexual orientation. The difference in people is in gender, culture, and race, social and psychological characteristics which make the workforce heterogeneous. Meaning individual characteristics of employees make them unique in the workplace. Workforce diversity is a determinant of leadership traits expression because it has the potential of influencing the leadership process. In the workplace, there are a lot of diversities that determine how things are done in relation to age diversity of employees, gender issues, educational background diversity, work experience issues and religion.

The diversity in these variables may influence positive leadership traits or negative leadership traits depending on myriad factors. Issues of gender diversity for instance may lead to critical issues of discrimination or fair treatment. Educational background diversity in the workplace may also determine the traits of leaders in relation to leadership behaviour and competency. This leads to conflict or opportunities for growth of business fortunes. Racially and ethnically diverse companies outperform industry norms by 35%. According to a survey conducted by Glassdoor (2020), 67% of job seekers agree that diverse workforce is important when considering job offers and 57% of employees think their companies should be more diverse.

On decision making characteristics, it is seen as process of checking and balancing system that keeps organisations growing both in vertical and linear directions in order to seek a goal. It has to do with making choices by identifying a decision, gathering information, and assessing alternative resolutions to maximize business opportunities. Therefore, the characteristics of decision - making determines the leader's traits. Creating an environment where staff members take ownership of work activities and to also participate in decision-making process is critical and that may influence the trait of leaders. That again may lead to the style of decision-making where leadership may choose to retain the final decision-making authority or use leadership power to collect information on how to determine what to do and how to do it in order to enhance organisation's growth. Decision-making style will determine whether there is consensus building or authoritarian decision making. Productive history-making characteristics possibly can determine leader's traits in relation to leadership styles and leadership competency demonstrated in the organisation's achievement of vision or agenda. Sharma (2022) asserts that effective decision involves two important aspects consisting; the purpose for which it is intended, and the environmental situation in which it is taken.

Most often than not even the best and correct decision may become ineffective if these aspects are not considered properly; because in decision-making there are so many inside and outside chains of unavoidable reactions. Strategic decisions determine organisation's success; whilst tactical decisions are about how things are done and operational decisions refer to decisions that are made each day to make organisations run.

Organisational climate is used for judging the employee sentiment about their employers' policies and practices. Organisational climate helps measure employee perceptions and also affects the priorities set by the

employees, their attitudes, and compliance in an attempt to contribute their quota to organisations effectiveness. Climate in organisations must promote professional environment that has a strong influence on the action and performance of employees in a workplace in order to indicate whether the expectations and beliefs of the individuals are fulfilled. According to Hassanpour et al (2019), organisational climate cover three dimensions: structural dimensions which refers to organisational structure, interactive dimensions which covers how employees communicate among themselves and perceptual dimensions dealing with how employees understand and relate to the climate within the working space. This actually determines the traits of leaders in the leadership process. It is therefore prudent for organisations to create a good climate within the working space to promote good leadership and organisational effectiveness. Bhasin (2022) asserts that the structure of organisations including rules, regulations and constraints; feelings of helpfulness in the work environment; perception of the relative risk in the work situation; the level of conflict and tolerance the work environment can tolerate; being confident of the appropriate records and individual responsibility of an employee can all influence the climate of organisations.

Bhasin (2022) concludes that excellent and positive work environment can motivate workforce and also boosts levels of performances leading to job satisfaction which is directly linked with efficiency levels of employees as it reduces turnover if found favorable.

Data Types, Sources and Processing:

The study used both primary and secondary data. The primary data were gathered using questionnaire administration in order to assess the determinants of leadership traits expression in private institutions of higher education. Questions on leader’s personality, organisational culture, workforce diversity, decision making and organisational climate were responded to. Data were processed using SmartLPS3 software.

Empirical Results and Analysis:

The expectations were that the determinants of leadership traits expression (personality, organisational culture, workforce diversity, decision making characteristics, external business environment, organisational structure and subordinate characteristics) would have a positive and significant effect on organisational effectiveness. The following model equation was used to describe the relationship between the determinants of leadership traits expression (leaders’ personality, organisational culture, workforce diversity, decision making, organisational climate) and organisational effectiveness.

Leadership Traits expression

$$= \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{Personality Traits}) + \beta_2 (\text{Organizational culture}) + \beta_3 (\text{Workforce diversity}) + \beta_4 (\text{Decision making}) + \beta_5 (\text{Organizational climate}) + \varepsilon$$

Where: Leadership traits expression is the outcome variable, whereas personality traits, organisational culture, workforce diversity, decision making characteristics, and organisational climate are predictor variables representing factors that influence leadership traits expression. β_0 is the intercept, representing the expected value of leadership traits expression when the predictor variables are equal to zero. $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4,$ and β_5 are representing the change in Leadership traits expression for a one-unit change in the corresponding predictor variable. ε is the error term, representing the random error or variation in leadership traits expression not explained by the predictor variables.

Leadership Traits Expression and Leaders Personality:

In the results, Table 1, removing components with Eigenvalues greater than 1 explains 83.761% of the variance in personality traits and 16.239% of the variance in leadership traits, respectively (1.648 and 0.312, respectively). This means that the first two factors discovered using the principal axis factoring method can account for 83.761% and 16.239%, respectively, of the second-order components.

Table 1: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.648	83.761	83.761	1.816	83.761	83.761
2	.168	16.239	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 1 displays the results of the variable correlation. Each of the two variables has a positive correlation with the other, implying a link with leadership traits expression. Therefore, leader’s personality accounts for 83.7% variations in leadership traits expression. The study revealed that personality traits have moderate association with leadership traits expressions. Personality explains 83.76% of the variance in leadership traits expression. Many studies on the relationship between leadership effectiveness and the big five personality traits (extraversion, conscientiousness, emotional stability, openness to experience, and agreeableness), reveals that certain personality traits, such as extraversion and conscientiousness, have been found to be more strongly related to leadership effectiveness than others and this is supported Judge et al (2002).

Leadership Traits Expression and Workforce Diversity:

All values less than 0.1 are ignored and thus deemed unimportant in the results. According to Table 2, removing the components with eigenvalues greater than one explains 56.731% of the variability in leadership

traits and 43.269 percent of the variability in work diversity, respectively (1.174 and 0.826, respectively). This means that the first two factors discovered using the principal axis factoring method can account for 56.731 percent and 43.269 percent, respectively, of the second-order components. A factor analysis was performed using principal axis factoring as the extraction method (a simple structure rotation) and the Oblimim with Kaiser normalisation as the rotation method to determine how the eleven variables relate to the two new extracted factors.

Table 2: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.174	56.731	56.7391	2.000	56.731	56.731
2	.826	43.269	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

According to Table 2 shows that leadership traits and the other two factors have weak correlation. Workforce diversity from the study explained 56.73% of the variance in leadership traits expression. The results of a study on the impact of leadership traits expression on workforce diversity and inclusion in the workplace showed that emotional intelligence, cultural intelligence, and ethical leadership are positively associated with diversity and inclusion outcomes. This finding supports Chan and Drasgow (2019) assertion that leaders can promote workplace diversity and inclusion by leveraging traits of emotional intelligence

Leadership Traits Expression and Organisational Climate:

Table 3 shows that isolating the four components with Eigenvalues greater than one explains 99.96% and 0.04% of the variances in leadership traits and organisational climate, respectively. This means that the first two factors discovered using the principal axis factoring method accounted for 99.96% and 0.04 percent of the second-order components, respectively.

Table 3: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.01	99.96	99.96	4.21	99.96	99.96
2	2.20	0.04	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The factor correlation results are shown in Table 3. Correlational research seeks to quantify the relationship between variables under consideration. According to Table 3, components 1 and 2 have a positive relationship. Correlation coefficients for factors 1 and 2 are 0.971 and 0.971, respectively. Each variable has a positive correlation with the other, implying a relationship with leadership traits expression. The study revealed that organisational climate accounted for 99.9 % variations in leadership traits expression. Guo, Wang, & Li, (2019) in the study on how authentic leadership affects organisational climate, the topic of authentic leadership's influence on climate is explored. Their results show that genuine leaders are more likely to foster a positive workplace culture by encouraging trust, open communication, and ethical behaviour, which in turn raises employee satisfaction, commitment, and engagement levels.

Leadership Traits Expression and Decision-Making Characteristics:

According to Table 4, isolating the components with Eigenvalues greater than one can account for (94.721% and 5.279%) of the variation in leadership traits and decision making (0.981 and 0.091, respectively). As a result, the Principal Axis Factoring Method's first two factors can account for 94.721 and 5.279 percent of the second-order components, respectively.

Table 4: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	0.981	94.721	94.721	1.072	96.102	96.102
2	0.091	5.279	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The factor correlation results are shown in Table 4 and the components 1 and 2 have a positive relationship. Correlation coefficients for factors 1 and 2 are 1.00 and 0.891, respectively. Each variable has a positive correlation with the other, implying a relationship with leadership traits expression. The results showed that decision making characteristics accounted for 94.7 % of the variations in leadership traits expression. Transformational leadership traits, such as visioning and problem-solving, are associated with rational decision-making styles, whereas transactional leadership traits, such as controlling and monitoring, are associated with non-rational decision-making styles, such as intuitive decision-making.

Leadership Traits Expression and Organisational Culture:

According to Table 5, isolating the components with Eigenvalues greater than one can account for (88.539% and 11.461%) of the variation in leadership traits and organisational culture (0.764 and 0.075,

respectively). As a result, the Principal Axis Factoring Method's first two factors can account for 88.539 and 11.461 percent of the second-order components, respectively.

Table 5: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	0.764	88.539	88.539	0.839	88.539	88.539
2	0.075	11.461	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The factor correlation results are shown in Table 5. Correlational research seeks to quantify how strong variables are related within a given context. According to Table 5, components 1 and 2 have a positive relationship. Correlation coefficients for factors 1 and 2 are 1.000 and 0.785, respectively. Each variable has a positive correlation with the other, implying a relationship with leadership traits expression. It was evident from the study that organisational culture accounted for 88.5% of the variations in leadership traits expression. The study revealed that organisational culture contributed more variations in leadership traits expression. Leadership philosophies affect organisational culture. According to the research, transactional leadership is positively related to a bureaucratic culture, whereas transformational leadership is positively related to a supportive and innovative culture

Summary and Conclusions:

It emerged from the study that leader's personality, organisational culture, workforce diversity and decision-making characteristics as well as organizational climate had a positive and significant relationship with leadership traits expressions. The study found that organisational climate explains 99.96% variations in leadership traits expressions and therefore have statistically highly significant relationship with leadership traits expression in Marshalls University College. Leader's personality explained 83.76% variation in leadership traits expressions while workforce diversity explained 56.73% variation. Again, decision making characteristics explained 94.721% variance in leadership traits expressions while organisational culture explained 88.539% variation.

The study settled on five key determinants of Leadership traits expression which had positive and significant association with organisational effectiveness. They include leader's personality, organisational culture, workforce diversity, decision making characteristics and organisational climate. University leadership must develop strong personality that can influence effective operations. Organisational culture is associated to organisational effectiveness as it emerged from the study therefore an effective organisational culture must be established in private institutions of higher education for optimal results.

The policy implications are that, there is a need for training and retraining on leader's personality, organisational culture, organisational climate and decision-making characteristics for institutional leadership continually to build capacity to enhance effectiveness. This calls for budget allocation to organize seminars and conferences on the determinants of Leadership traits expression. Again, institutional leadership must foster strong organisational culture and climate to promote effectiveness. A workable policy on organisational culture/climate maintenance is needed is that regard.

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